

PRISMA Checklist for “Health Impacts Associated with Community Exposure to Industrial Animal Operations: A Protocol for a Systematic Review” by Semba et al.

PRISMA-P (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic review and Meta-Analysis Protocols) 2015 checklist: recommended items to address in a systematic review protocol*

Section and topic	Item No	Checklist item	Identified in our protocol
ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION			
Title:			
Identification	1a	Identify the report as a protocol of a systematic review	1a. See title and section 1.2
Update	1b	If the protocol is for an update of a previous systematic review, identify as such	1b. Not applicable
Registration	2	If registered, provide the name of the registry (such as PROSPERO) and registration number	
Authors:			
Contact	3a	Provide name, institutional affiliation, e-mail address of all protocol authors; provide physical mailing address of corresponding author	3a. See page 1
Contributions	3b	Describe contributions of protocol authors and identify the guarantor of the review	3b. See section 4.2, CRediT statement
Amendments	4	If the protocol represents an amendment of a previously completed or published protocol, identify as such and list changes; otherwise, state plan for documenting important protocol amendments	4. Not applicable
Support:			
Sources	5a	Indicate sources of financial or other support for the review	5a. See section 4.3
Sponsor	5b	Provide name for the review funder and/or sponsor	5b. See section 4.3
Role of sponsor or funder	5c	Describe roles of funder(s), sponsor(s), and/or institution(s), if any, in developing the protocol	5c. Our funder and sponsor had no role in developing our protocol
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	6	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known	6. See section 1.1, Rationale
Objectives	7	Provide an explicit statement of the question(s) the review will address with reference to participants, interventions, comparators, and outcomes (PICO)	7. See section 1.2, Objectives
METHODS			

Eligibility criteria	8	Specify the study characteristics (such as PICO, study design, setting, time frame) and report characteristics (such as years considered, language, publication status) to be used as criteria for eligibility for the review	8. See section 4.6.1, Table 1. Eligibility Criteria Using the PECO Framework
Information sources	9	Describe all intended information sources (such as electronic databases, contact with study authors, trial registers or other grey literature sources) with planned dates of coverage	9. See section 4.6.1., Table 1. Eligibility Criteria Using the PECO Framework
Search strategy	10	Present draft of search strategy to be used for at least one electronic database, including planned limits, such that it could be repeated	10. See section 4.6.2., Table 2. Proposed Search Strategy for Medline (Ovid)
Study records:			
Data management	11a	Describe the mechanism(s) that will be used to manage records and data throughout the review	11a. See section 2.4.1 Data management
Selection process	11b	State the process that will be used for selecting studies (such as two independent reviewers) through each phase of the review (that is, screening, eligibility and inclusion in meta-analysis)	11b. See section 2.4.2 Selection process 11c. See section 2.4.3 Data collection process
Data collection process	11c	Describe planned method of extracting data from reports (such as piloting forms, done independently, in duplicate), any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators	12. See section 4.6.3. Table 3. Data Extraction Sheet
Data items	12	List and define all variables for which data will be sought (such as PICO items, funding sources), any pre-planned data assumptions and simplifications	
Outcomes and prioritization	13	List and define all outcomes for which data will be sought, including prioritization of main and additional outcomes, with rationale	13. See section 1.2, Objectives and Section 4.6.5. Table 4. Examples of Health Outcomes
Risk of bias in individual studies	14	Describe anticipated methods for assessing risk of bias of individual studies, including whether this will be done at the outcome or study level, or both; state how this information will be used in data synthesis	14. See section 2.7 Risk of bias in individual studies
Data synthesis	15a	Describe criteria under which study data will be quantitatively synthesised	15a. See section 2.8 Data synthesis
	15b	If data are appropriate for quantitative synthesis, describe planned summary measures, methods of handling data and methods of combining data from studies, including any planned exploration of consistency (such as I^2 , Kendall's τ)	15b. See section 2.8 Data synthesis
	15c	Describe any proposed additional analyses (such as sensitivity or subgroup analyses, meta-regression)	15c. See section 2.8 Data synthesis
	15d	If quantitative synthesis is not appropriate, describe the type of summary planned	15d. See section 2.8 Data synthesis
Meta-bias(es)	16	Specify any planned assessment of meta-bias(es) (such as publication bias across studies, selective reporting within studies)	16. See section 2.9 Meta-bias(es)

Confidence in cumulative evidence	17 Describe how the strength of the body of evidence will be assessed (such as GRADE)	17. See section 2.10 Confidence in cumulative evidence
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*** It is strongly recommended that this checklist be read in conjunction with the PRISMA-P Explanation and Elaboration (cite when available) for important clarification on the items. Amendments to a review protocol should be tracked and dated. The copyright for PRISMA-P (including checklist) is held by the PRISMA-P Group and is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution Licence 4.0.**

From: Shamseer L, Moher D, Clarke M, Ghersi D, Liberati A, Petticrew M, Shekelle P, Stewart L, PRISMA-P Group. Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015: elaboration and explanation. BMJ. 2015 Jan 2;349(jan02 1):g7647.